

**A STUDY OF RELATIONSHIP OF VALUES AND JOB SATISFACTION OF
SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS****Dr. Jyoti Khajuria*****Assistance Professor,**Department of Education, Kurukshetra University***Ashu Arora*******Research Scholar,**Department of Education, Kurukshetra University.***Abstract**

The present study was undertaken to analyse the values (theoretical, economic, aesthetic, social, political and religious) and job satisfaction of male and female secondary school teachers. The sample was selected randomly from various Government Secondary/ Senior Secondary Schools in district Fatehabad, Haryana. The data was collected with the help of Job Satisfaction Scale developed and validated by Dr.(Mrs.) Meera Dixit and Teacher Values Inventory developed and validated by Dr.(Mrs.) Harbhajan L.Singh and Dr. S.P.Ahluwalia. The collected data was analysed by using mean, standard deviation, t-ratio and pearson product moment correlation. No significant correlation was found between job satisfaction and values (theoretical, economic,aesthetic,social,political and religious) of secondary school teachers. Between male and female secondary school teachers, no significant difference was found for theoretical, economic, aesthetic, political and social values, while for religious values difference was found to be significant. Male and female secondary school teachers do not differ significantly on job satisfaction

Introduction

Education plays pivotal role in the development of a country and it is mainly imparted by teachers. So, teachers are the builders of a nation. A society or a nation can progress only with the help of its teachers. It is the teacher who draws maximum impact on the personality of an

individual in its formative years, which remains all through its life. A teacher's behaviour can make or mar a student's life. In spite of the importance of teachers, they have their particular place and position in the society. There are various factors, which affect them and in due course affect their work. Such factors are internal and external. Among so many factors, values and job satisfaction have their own effect on the work and effectiveness of secondary school teachers.

Values play an important role in the life of an individual. The values of an individual are the chief determinant of his/her behaviour. These influence life and works of an individual and provide meaning and direction to his/her life. Different types of values like theoretical, social, political, aesthetic, religious and economic etc. act as a motivating force in the behaviour of an individual. Values shape the most of man's activities. These help the individual in having interest in one or other profession. Job satisfaction reflects employees' overall assessment of their job particularly their emotions, behaviour and attitude about their work experience. The happier the people are within their job, the more satisfied they are said to be. In schools job satisfaction means teachers' internal and external satisfaction from their jobs. Gupta and Jain(2003) reported that a variety of factors such as salary, security, physical conditions, promotion, recognition etc. influence job satisfaction. In another study by Kaur and Sidana(2011), the level of job satisfaction of male teachers was found to be greater than their female counterparts. While Gupta, Pasrija and Bansal(2012) reported that female teachers were more satisfied than their male counterparts. The dissatisfaction of the teachers with their work does not affect only them but affect their schools too, such teachers can develop negative reactions against their job. Yilmaz and Dilmac(2011) investigated teachers values and job satisfaction and found a meaningful relationship between job satisfaction and humanitarian values and power, success, hedonism, excitation, self control, universality, charitableness, traditionality and safety sub magnitudes. Bandhana(2011) found no significant difference in values(T,E,A,S,R,P) among male Kendriya Vidyalaya Teachers with high job satisfaction and low job satisfaction and also among female teachers with high and low job satisfaction. Antim Kumari, Kiran Sharma(2012) studied and found that work values are significantly related to job satisfaction, female teachers have higher level of work values than male teachers. Gangadharrao(2012) investigated and found that teachers are satisfied in their job while female teachers are comparatively more satisfied than their male counterparts. Nadeem et al(2013) investigated that rural and urban secondary school teachers do not differ significantly on job satisfaction. Gupta and Gehlawat(2013) found no

significant difference in the job satisfaction and work motivation of male and female teachers respectively. Unless and until a teacher derives satisfaction he can not initiate desirable outcomes to cater to the needs of the society as well as to live up to the expectations of the school also.

Justification of the Study

Every point of the educational system revolves around the students and the teachers. In education among other factors, values and job satisfaction have considerable importance especially for teachers. Values, which provide the key to a more adequate understanding of man, are so much important for teachers as teachers play a significant role in inculcating values among students. It is also essential to get the knowledge about their job as it is necessary that they feel happy and contented in their work if effective teaching is to be expected from them. It has been noticed that job satisfaction is a composition of many factors, which play considerable role in making a person fully satisfied with the job. These factors include sex, age, time on job, intelligence, personality and education. Knowledge of teachers' values and job satisfaction may provide a clear distinction to school administrators and policy makers in identifying school programmes and activities, it will also help to bring to light some of the problems and needs of the teachers. Thus teachers' values and job satisfaction are considered as important factors to be studied. In the light of the above discussion, it has been decided to take the study of values and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers.

Statement of the Problem

A Study of Relationship of Values and Job Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers.

Operational Definitions of the Terms Used

Values

According to Allport(1969): "Anything that yields a satisfaction or provides a mean for such satisfaction is designated as value". In the present study, theoretical, economic, political, social, aesthetic and religious values are taken into consideration.

Job Satisfaction

It is the way an employee feels about his/her job. It is generalized attitude towards the job based on evaluation of different aspects of the job.

Secondary School Teachers

Here, Secondary School Teachers stand for teachers who impart education from 6th to 10th class in Government schools of Haryana.

Objectives of the Study

1. To investigate the relationship between values and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers.
2. To compare the values of male and female secondary school teachers.
3. To compare the job satisfaction of male and female secondary school teachers.

Hypotheses

1. There exists significant relationship between values and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers.
2. There exists significant difference in the values of male and female secondary school teachers.
3. There exists significant difference in the job satisfaction of male and female secondary school teachers.

Delimitations

1. The study is delimited to Fatehabad district of Haryana.
2. The study is further delimited to 10 Government schools of Fatehabad district only.
3. The study is also delimited to 26 male and 26 female teachers teaching at secondary school level only.

Method

In the present study, descriptive survey method has been used.

Sample

For the present study, 10 Government Schools were selected randomly from Fatehabad district. From these schools fifty two teachers (26 male and 26 female) were selected randomly, who teach at secondary level.

Tools used

1. Teacher Value Inventory (1994) by Dr. (Mrs.) Harbhajan L. Singh and Dr. S.P. Ahulwalia was used to measure teachers' values. It involves theoretical, economical, aesthetic, social, political and religious values.
2. Dixit's job satisfaction scale (D.J.S.S.) (1993) by Dr. (Mrs.) Meera Dixit was used to measure the job satisfaction level of teachers. It covers following job factors-
 - (a) Intrinsic aspect of the job
 - (b) Salary promotion of avenues and service conditions
 - (c) Physical facilities
 - (d) Institutional plans and policies
 - (e) Satisfaction with social status and family welfare
 - (f) Satisfaction with authorities
 - (g) Report with students
 - (h) Relationship with co-workers.

Statistical Techniques used

Mean, S.D. , t-test, and Pearson Product Moment Correlation.

Analysis and Interpretation

- 1. Relationship between values and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers.**

Table – 1.

Values	Job Satisfaction (r)	Correlation
Theoretical	-0.06	Insignificant
Economic	-0.12	Insignificant
Aesthetic	-0.14	Insignificant
Political	-0.24	Insignificant
Social	+0.24	Insignificant
Religious	-0.24	Insignificant

n=52, degree of freedom = n-2, level of significance – 0.05 and 0.01

Table – 1 shows the correlation of values and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers. It is clear from the table that between job satisfaction and theoretical, economic, aesthetic, political, social and religious values the relationship is insignificant.

2. Difference between values of male and female secondary school teachers.

Table – 2

Values	Male(26)	Female(26)	SE-D	't'- ratio	Significant/ Insignificant
	Mean	Mean			
Theoretical	44.4	44.4	9.498	0	Insignificant
Economic	47.56	49.03	2.58	-0.569	Insignificant
Aesthetic	46.9	42.52	2.399	1.825	Insignificant
Political	46.96	46.04	2.77	0.332	Insignificant
Social	45.4	49.35	3.387	-1.165	Insignificant
Religious	45.44	50.77	2.384	-2.235	Significant*

Level of Significance –0.05 and 0.01,

* Significant at 0.05 level while insignificant at 0.01 level.

Table –2 reveals no significant difference between theoretical, economic, aesthetic, political and social values of male and female secondary school teachers at 0.05 and 0.01 levels of significance. While for religious values at 0.05 level , significant difference is found between male and female secondary school teachers and at 0.01 level, this difference is found to be insignificant.

3. Difference between job satisfaction of male and female secondary school teachers.

Table –3

Group	N	Mean	SE-D	't'-ratio	Significant/ Insignificant
Male	26	137.65	9.49	-0.421	Insignificant
Female	26	141.65			

Level of significance - 0.05 and 0.01

Table –3 depicts no significant difference between job satisfaction of male and female secondary school teachers at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significance, hence the hypothesis that there is significant difference between job satisfaction of male and female secondary school teachers is rejected.

Major Findings-

1. It is found that there is no significant relationship between job satisfaction and theoretical, economic, aesthetic, social, political and religious values of secondary school teachers. Hence, the hypothesis that there is significant relationship between values and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers is rejected.
2. It is found that there is no significant difference between theoretical, economic, aesthetic, political and social values of male and female secondary school teachers. Hence for these values the hypothesis is rejected. While at 0.05 level, significant difference is found between religious values of male and female secondary school teachers.
3. No significant difference is found between job satisfaction of male and female secondary school teachers. Hence, the hypothesis that there is significant difference between job satisfaction of male and female secondary school teachers is rejected.

Conclusion-

From the above findings, it can be concluded that male and female teachers are satisfied with their jobs, moreover no significant difference is found between their job satisfaction. No significant relationship is found between job satisfaction and theoretical, economic, aesthetic, social, political and religious values of secondary school teachers. For religious values male and female secondary school teachers differ significantly and for other values no significant difference is found between them. This study may be helpful for administrators and heads of schools in taking decisions regarding teachers and school activities. The problems and needs of the teachers should be duly treated for enhancing their effectiveness and efficiency. They will perform better and would be more enthusiastic in helping students and inculcating desirable values among the learners.

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